

ISic3609

I.Sicily inscription 3609

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Priolo Gargallo, church of S. Foca, contrada Manomozza

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 30671

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645682

Bibliography

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undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

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siracusano: recenti indagini a Priolo Gargallo. In Bonacasa Carra, R.M., Vitale, E. (eds.), *La cristianizzazione in Italia fra tardoantico e altomedioevo*. Palermo. pp. 1647-1672. At 1654 n.26

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